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Visual poetry and artistic creation processes of Brazilian indigenous peoples: body adornments

Fabio Rossano Dario^{1,2,*}
(Ethnobiological Researcher)

¹ The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin
Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

² Ploaia Agronomia, Ecologia e Meio Ambiente
Rua Leonardo Mota, 66 - São Paulo-SP, ZIP 05586-090, Brazil

*E-mail address: fabiorossano@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

The artistic traditions of Brazil's Indigenous peoples are rich and deeply symbolic, manifesting in various forms of expression, including body painting, pottery, basketry, ornaments, tools, decorative objects, hunting and fishing gear, and musical instruments. These artworks are crafted from natural materials found in their surroundings, such as vines, leaves, bark, seeds, feathers, and animal teeth. This study aimed to explore the richness of visual poetry and the artistic creation processes of certain Indigenous peoples in Brazil, with a particular focus on body adornments, including headdresses, necklaces, bracelets, earrings, and rings.

Keywords: Indigenous, ethnoconservation, headdress, necklace, bracelet, earring, ring

1. INTRODUCTION

Many of the world's most biodiverse regions are inhabited by traditional communities, whose profound ecological knowledge and culturally embedded relationships with the environment contribute significantly to the sustainable management of natural resources. Their primary contributions to biodiversity conservation encompass not only the sustainable use and

management of these resources but also the preservation and transmission of traditional ecological knowledge and cultural practices [1-3].

To maintain the social continuity of their communities, traditional populations engage in a mix of economic activities, including plant extraction, subsistence farming, hunting, and fishing. The artistic traditions of Brazilian Indigenous peoples are diverse and deeply symbolic, reflected in various forms of creative expression. These include body painting, ceramics, basket weaving, featherwork, decorative items, tools for work and traditional festivals, ornaments, hunting equipment, and musical instruments. These creations are crafted using natural resources such as vines, leaves, bark, seeds, bird feathers, and animal teeth.

Within these activities, myths, rituals, and symbolic elements play a central role. In the context of the technical and social division of labor, artisanal practices are particularly significant, as the producer and their family maintain comprehensive control over the entire production process. Economic exchanges with external markets are limited, given that production is primarily oriented toward subsistence, thereby restricting opportunities for capital accumulation.

The data presented here were obtained during fieldwork conducted as part of several studies on the risks and impacts of project implementation on the lives of Indigenous communities. These studies complement environmental impact assessments. This paper aims to showcase the visual poetry and artistic creation processes of certain Brazilian Indigenous peoples, with a focus on headdresses, necklaces, bracelets, earrings, and rings.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study involved Indigenous peoples from the Brazilian Amazon, including the Apiaká, Arara, Juruna (who identify as Yudjá), Kayabi, Tenharim (who identify as Kagwahiva), Mura, and Sateré Mawé ethnic groups, as well as Indigenous groups from the Savannah biome, including the Bororo, Guarani Kaiowá, and Guarani Nhandeva. The research was conducted with the authorization of the Indigenous communities and the National Indigenous People Foundation (FUNAI), the Brazilian governmental agency responsible for Amerindian interests and culture. Interviews were conducted with the Bororo in August 2010, the Apiaká and Kayabi in June 2011, the Guarani Kaiowá and Guarani Nhandeva throughout 2014 and 2015, the Kagwahiva in October and November 2014, the Mura and Sateré Mawé in January and February 2016 and March 2018, and the Arara and Juruna in 2019.

One of the study regions is known as the “Volta Grande do Xingu” (Big Bend of the Xingu River), located in the state of Pará, Brazil, between latitudes 03°23'S and 03°38'S and longitudes 51°33'W and 52°00'W. This 130 km stretch of rapids and braided channels on the Xingu River, a major tributary of the Amazon River, is home to Indigenous peoples of the Arara and Juruna ethnic groups.

The Indigenous people of the Kagwahiva ethnic group live in the Tenharim Marmelos Indigenous Land, located entirely within the state of Amazonas, in the municipalities of Humaitá and Manicoré, between geographic coordinates 7°48' and 8°53' south latitude and 61°35' and 62°10' west longitude. In the past, before the construction of the Trans-Amazonian Highway, these Indigenous people lived together in a single village on the banks of the Marmelos River, in the area where the highway now crosses the river.

Indigenous people of the Mura and Sateré Mawé ethnic groups live in the Rio Urubu Indigenous Territory, located in the municipality of Itacoatiara, in the state of Amazonas, on the left bank of the Amazon River. This territory lies between latitudes 02°59'S and 03°12'S, and longitudes 58°04'W and 59°48'W. Other study areas include the Kayabi and Apiaká Indigenous territories. The Apiaká territory studied is located in Mato Grosso State, in the southern Brazilian Amazon Rainforest, on the left bank of the Teles Pires River, within the Apiacás municipal district. It lies between 07°39'S and 08°32'S latitude and 57°50'W and 58°21'W longitude. The Kayabi territory studied spans the states of Pará and Mato Grosso, covering parts of the municipalities of Jacareacanga (southwest Pará) and Apiacás (northern Mato Grosso), along the Teles Pires River. It lies between 07°54'S and 09°13'S latitude and 56°39'W and 57°54'W longitude.

The Indigenous Bororo studied live in the Meruri village, located in the state of Mato Grosso. It is situated between latitudes 15°23'S and 15°44'S, and longitudes 52°51'W and 53°13'W. The indigenous Guarani Kaiowá and Guarani Nandeva studied live in different villages located in Mato Grosso do Sul State, near the BR-163 highway, between 21°45'S and 23°12'S latitude and 53°55'W and 54°58'W longitude.

Data collection was conducted through open and semi-structured interviews [4], allowing for greater flexibility and a more natural dialogue [5]. Indigenous individuals of both genders and various ages, recommended by their communities for their knowledge, were interviewed regarding the identification, collection, and utilization of raw materials for headdresses, necklaces, bracelets, earrings, and rings.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A large part of the techniques used by the Indigenous people interviewed in the making of handicrafts were learned from their ancestors, and this information reveals that the art of crafting handicrafts is characterized by learning within the family setting. To ensure the social reproduction of the group, these populations combine various economic activities, such as plant extraction, small-scale farming, hunting, and fishing. Indigenous art is primarily related to the creation of work tools, decorative pieces, items used in traditional festivals, as well as gifts and handicrafts with economic purposes. The raw materials are sourced from nature, such as vines, leaves, bark, fibers, seeds from a wide variety of plant species, feathers, and animal teeth and bones.

The headdress is one of the main traditional ornaments used by various Indigenous ethnic groups in Brazil and holds significant symbolism in their culture [6]. Typically made from feathers of different bird species, it can represent various meanings, such as identity, history, connection with nature and ancestors, responsibility, and respect. Its use may be restricted to individuals in specific social positions, such as chiefs and shamans. Headdresses are often worn during ceremonies, such as weddings, traditional festivals, and "rites of passage," which are ceremonies that mark important transitions in the lives of Brazilian Indigenous peoples, such as birth, puberty, marriage, and death.

During interviews with Juruna artisans, they identified species of wild fauna they hunt, classifying these animals based on their utility. They highlighted the use of feathers from 18 bird species to make headdresses and teeth from 10 animal species to make necklaces (Table 1):

Table 1. Wild animals hunted by the Juruna for the use of feathers and teeth in the making of headdresses and necklaces.

Use	Ethnospecies	English names	Taxon names
Feather for making headdresses	Azulona	Gray Tinamou	<i>Tinamus tao</i>
	Jacupemba	Rusty-margined Guan	<i>Penelope superciliaris</i>
	Jacupiranga	White-crested Guan	<i>Penelope pileata</i>
	Jacu-cujubim	Red-throated Piping-Guan	<i>Aburria kujubi</i>
	Mutum-pinima	Wattled Curassow	<i>Crax fasciolata</i>
	Mutum-cavalo	Razor-billed Curassow	<i>Pauxi tuberosa</i>
	Socó-boi	Rufescent Tiger-Heron	<i>Tigrisoma lineatum</i>
	Gavião-pedrez	Gray-lined Hawk	<i>Buteo nitidus</i>
	Gavião-real	Harpy Eagle	<i>Harpia harpyja</i>
	Cigana	Hoatzin	<i>Opisthocomus hoazin</i>
	Tucano-de-papo-branco	White-throated Toucan	<i>Ramphastos tucanus</i>
	Tucano	Channel-billed Toucan	<i>Ramphastos vitellinus</i>
	Arara-azul	Hyacinth Macaw	<i>Anodorhynchus hyacinthinus</i>
	Araracanga	Scarlet Macaw	<i>Ara macao</i>
	Arara-vermelha	Red-and-green Macaw	<i>Ara chloropterus</i>
	Maracanã	Chestnut-fronted Macaw	<i>Ara severus</i>
	Papagaio-moleiro	Mealy Parrot	<i>Amazona farinosa</i>
Papagaio	Orange-winged Parrot	<i>Amazona amazonica</i>	
Tooth for making necklaces	Caititu	Collared Peccary	<i>Pecari tajacu</i>
	Porcão	White-lipped Peccary	<i>Tayassu pecari</i>
	Guariba	Red-handed Howler Monkey	<i>Alouatta belzebul</i>
	Macaco-prego	Guianan Brown Tufted Capuchin	<i>Sapajus apella</i>
	Mão-de-ouro	Common Squirrel Monkey	<i>Saimiri sciureus</i>

	Onça-pintada	Jaguar	<i>Panthera onca</i>
	Onça-vermelha	Cougar	<i>Puma concolor</i>
	Onça-preta	Jaguar	<i>Panthera onca</i>
	Jacaré	White Caiman	<i>Caiman crocodilus</i>
	Peixe-cachorra	Payara	<i>Hydrolycus scomberoides</i>

Just like the Juruna, their neighbors, the Arara, create beautiful headdresses, bracelets, and necklaces using bird feathers. The most commonly used feathers for these crafts are from macaws (*Ara macao* and *Ara chloropterus*), parrots (*Amazona* spp.), toucans (*Ramphastos* spp.), and curassows (*Pauxi tuberosa* and *Crax fasciolata*) (Figure 1). Feather art by Brazilian Indigenous peoples is one of the most renowned and striking forms of expression in Brazil's native cultures. The usual definition of feather art refers to objects crafted with bird feathers, often combined with other materials, and primarily used as body ornaments, either for everyday wear or for solemn and ritualized purposes.

Feather art can be categorized into two main types. The first consists of long feathers mounted on rigid supports, creating artifacts with a grand and monumental appearance - most notably exemplified by large headdresses (Figure 2). The second type involves the use of small feathers attached to flexible bases, producing a more delicate and intricate aesthetic, commonly observed in bracelets, loincloths, belts, necklaces, and anklets (Figures 3 to 7).

Indigenous necklaces are an artistic expression that represents the cultural identity of Brazilian Indigenous peoples. Handmade, these necklaces are a way to preserve and transmit Indigenous culture and traditions. These necklaces are typically made from seeds of herbaceous, shrub, and tree plant species, feathers from various bird species, twigs, vines, beads, animal teeth and bones, latex, and other materials. The patterns, colors, and types of materials used can indicate the ethnicity or region of origin of the artisan. Some Brazilian Indigenous peoples are using beads imported from the Czech Republic to make necklaces, bracelets, and other accessories. These beads are known for their excellent quality and consistent size.

In some Indigenous villages, the making of bracelets and necklaces with colored beads was observed as a replacement for seeds. The beadwork is very well done: the beads can be arranged in geometric patterns and striking colors. However, there seems to be a partial substitution of seeds with beads. In one Arara village, I observed a well-crafted necklace where the contrast between the artificial beads and a peccary tooth (*Tayassu pecari*) was quite striking.

Among the seeds used by the Arara in the making of necklaces, bracelets, and rings, palm species stand out, such as *tucum* (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*), *inajá* (*Attalea maripa*), *pati* (*Syagrus cocoides*), and especially *mumbaca* (*Astrocaryum gynacanthum*). Other important seeds used for the same purposes include those from the tree known as *mulungu* (*Erythrina amazonica*), which has a reddish color, as well as seeds from the *arapá* vine (species unidentified) and the *banana-braba* (*Phenakospermum guyannense*).

The plants used in handicrafts hold great cultural importance for the Arara, being part of the ethnosppecies that are avoided when clearing land for planting, for example: "We don't cut down the *tucum* [*Astrocaryum aculeatum*] to make our crafts, we need it a lot to make rings,

necklaces, earrings" (M.P.S. Arara, 52 years old, ♀, Arara ethnic group, Itkoum village, Arara's Big Bend of Xingu Indigenous Land, July 12, 2019).

Figure 1. Details of some bird species whose feathers are used by the indigenous people of the Amazon to make headdresses, necklaces, and bracelets: (A) *Ramphastos tucanus*; (B) *Ara macao*; (C) *Ara severus*; (D) *Amazona farinosa*; (E) *Opisthocomus hoazin*.

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

The crafting of necklaces by the Guarani is carried out exclusively by women, who use a wide variety of seeds from herbaceous, shrub, tree, and vine plant species. One frequently used seed is from the *olho-de-boi* tree, or *ñaé* in the indigenous language (*Ormosia arborea*), which is red and black. In contrast to this striking seed, the indigenous people use black-colored seeds from the *piri* plant or *mbaraka'y* (*Canna pedunculata*) and from the trees *aguai* (*Chrysophyllum gonocarpum*), *pau-ferro* (*Libidibia ferrea*), and *jueirana* (*Parkia pendula*). The *jueirana* is a tree species from the Atlantic Forest biome, and its seeds reach these indigenous people, located

in the central-west region of Brazil, through the exchange of raw materials with Guarani indigenous groups living in the state of Espírito Santo, along the Brazilian coast. The indigenous people also use seeds from exotic species in necklace crafting, including the red seeds of the "pau-brasil" (Brazilwood) a name attributed to *Adenanthera pavonina*, a tree species native to India and Malaysia that was introduced in Brazil for urban landscaping. Seeds from the *leucena* (*Leucaena leucocephala*), a tree native to Central America, are also widely used.

A Guarani Kaiowá artisan interviewed crafts rings, bracelets, earrings, and necklaces. The making of her pieces is delicately executed using raw materials available in nature, such as seeds, vines, and bird feathers - not all of them wild- since dyed feathers from the helmeted guineafowl (*Numida meleagris*) are also used, adding a special highlight to some pieces. The quality of the products created by this artisan demonstrates great skill and a high level of aesthetic care. The works are made with attention to detail, featuring colors that harmonize with each other, and the objects are sold at her home.

Another Guarani Kaiowá artisan, endowed with enormous creativity, an incredible aesthetic sense, and remarkable organization, keeps seeds from dozens of plant species stored in glass containers. She crafts beautiful necklaces by combining different raw materials, such as seeds, vines, feathers, wild pig teeth, and even *Brachiaria* grass (*Brachiaria decumbens*), which, when dried and braided, forms delicate details in the necklaces. For the Guarani, the function of necklaces, beyond the implicit aesthetic appeal of wearing an ornament, is also religious: "God protects with the necklace so that nothing happens, no disease" (V.V. Gonçalves, ♂, Guarani Kaiowá ethnic group, Panambi Indigenous Reserve, July 19, 2014).

The ritual attire of the Tenharim is highly diverse. During visits to Tenharim villages, we were shown feathered artifacts such as headdresses, bracelets, wristbands, anklets, and necklaces. The manufacturing process involves several preliminary activities, including gathering materials from the forest, hunting birds or collecting feathers from captive birds [e.g., the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*), the blue-and-yellow macaw (*Ara ararauna*), and the blue-headed parrot (*Pionus menstruus*)], selection and classification, material preparation, and the preparation of accessory materials. Much of the feather art is closely related to weaving, as the feathers are attached through tying and braiding fibers, such as cotton cultivated within the villages themselves.

The *akanitara* is a head ornament (headdress) usually made with parrot and macaw feathers, as is the *tapakura* (bracelet). Beautiful headdresses have been recorded in Tenharim villages, mainly crafted with feathers from the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*), but also from the helmeted curassow (*Pauxi tuberosa*) and tinamous (*Crypturellus* spp.). While some feathered artifacts can be worn in daily life, the more elaborate and significant ones are reserved for ceremonies, such as *Mboatawa*, the main ritual of the Tenharim people.

In the crafting of necklaces (*mboy'ra*), a task typically performed by Tenharim women, a wide variety of seeds from herbaceous, shrub, tree, and vine species are used. The most commonly used seed is the small nut of the *tucumã* palm (*yvahua*, *Astrocaryum aculeatum*), which is collected in large quantities and broken into different sizes. These pieces are then manually pierced to allow the passage of a thread that will hold them together. Only afterward are they sanded to achieve a uniform and high-quality final product.

Other seeds used by the Tenharim in necklace making include those from the *agañanguagy* vine, the herbaceous species *tamutu* (*Canna indica*) and *piriquiteira* (*Cochlospermum orinocense*), as well as seeds from the trees *castanha-de-arara* (*Jaywuhu*, *Joannesia heveoides*), *jatobá* (*Hymenaea* spp.), *fava* (*Albizia duckeana*), and *paricá* (*Parkia*

multijuga). Additionally, small nuts from the palm species *tucumãzinho* (*Astrocaryum gynacanthum*), *inajá* (*Attalea maripa*), and *paxiúba* (*pytoma*, *Socratea exorrhiza*) are also used.

The seed of the *paricá* (*yuruarapé* or *iwyrwarapéuwa*, *Parkia multijuga*) is important in necklace making, which is why "it holds great cultural value; the Indigenous people avoid cutting it down because it does not bear fruit every year." Despite the traditional use of the seed, caution is needed when interacting with this species, as "touching the tree calls the rain" and "holding the seed can bring a storm" (D. Tenharim, 84 years old, ♂, Kagwahiva ethnic group, Hawk clan, Kampinhu village, Tenharim Marmelos Indigenous Land, November 11, 2014).

The necklaces of the Kayabi and Apiaká are usually crafted by women of different ages using fruits from the *tucum* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*) and the *inajá* palm (*Attalea maripa*). These fruits are processed and transformed into small smooth beads or delicate zoomorphic figures. Some of these pieces are made in combination with other raw materials, such as colorful seeds from various Amazonian species, as well as bird feathers.

Among the Mura, feathered artifacts such as headdresses and necklaces are rare. In necklace making, a variety of seeds from different plant species are used, with the nuts of the *tucumã* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*) being the most commonly employed. These nuts are collected and broken into different sizes, drilled to allow the passage of the thread that will join them, and only then are they sanded to achieve a homogeneous product with the desired quality. *Tucumã* or *tucum* refers to the same species, *Astrocaryum aculeatum*, a palm tree commonly found in open areas with poor and degraded soils. It can reach up to 15 meters in height, with a trunk covered in long, thin spines.

The crafting of feather art by the Bororo holds both economic and symbolic-ritual significance. In addition to being the most commercially accepted type of handicraft with the highest market value, feathered attire and accessories are essential elements of material culture in Bororo rituals and ceremonies. Each sub-clan has its own distinctive adornments, primarily made from macaw feathers. Headdresses, called *pariko* in Bororo, are both works of art and artifacts that serve to identify and distinguish the sub-clans.

Among the species identified by the Bororo, the most important are those used in Indigenous feather art, such as macaws (*Ara macao* and *Ara ararauna*), parrots (*Pionus menstruus*, *Amazona amazonica*, and *Amazona aestiva*), toucans and aracaris (*Ramphastos toco* and *Pteroglossus castanotis*), curassows (*Penelope superciliaris* and *Crax fasciolata*), tinamous (*Crypturellus parvirostris* and *Crypturellus undulatus*), herons (*Ardea alba* and *Egretta thula*), and hawks (*Herpetotheres cachinnans* and *Caracara plancus*). The Bororo primarily use feathers for making bracelets and headdresses. They also use toucan beaks to create handicrafts [7].

The Bororo are particularly fond of using the yellow feathers of the aracari (*Pteroglossus castanotis*) for making bracelets and the long tail feathers of macaws for crafting headdresses - blue feathers from *Ara ararauna* and red feathers from *Ara macao*. *Ara ararauna* is the most common macaw in Bororo territory, whereas *Ara macao* is very rare in their lands but remains the most highly prized bird among the Bororo [7].

Some of these birds are raised in the Meruri village. The practice of raising wild birds in Brazil originates from Indigenous traditions, as Indigenous peoples also incorporate avian elements into their legends, myths, superstitions, songs, rituals, and rock paintings. For this reason, the Bororo keep birds as pets, referring to them as *xerimbabos*, a word of Indigenous (Tupi-Guarani) origin meaning "my dear thing." [7]

Macaws, which are hunted and kept as *xerimbabos* (wild animals raised as pets), are cared for by Indigenous people not only because their feathers are used in ornaments but also because they provide comfort to the souls of deceased Bororo through metempsychosis - the transmigration of the soul at death into another body, whether human or animal [8].

The Bororo believe in reincarnation after death. When a person dies, their soul, which the Bororo call *aroe*, moves into the body of certain animals. Bororo feather art serves as a tribute to death, with the most significant ornaments primarily crafted for funeral ceremonies. While it may seem paradoxical, it is precisely through funerals that Bororo society reaffirms the vitality of its cultural life [9].

4. CONCLUSION

Body adornments, such as headdresses, necklaces, bracelets, earrings, and rings, play a vital role in the cultural traditions of the Indigenous groups studied. Typically handcrafted by women, these ornaments are worn on various occasions, including weddings, traditional festivals, and rites of passage - ceremonies that mark significant life transitions among Brazilian Indigenous peoples, such as birth, puberty, marriage, and death.

Certain adornments, like headdresses, may be reserved for individuals of specific social status, such as chiefs and shamans, and can symbolize identity, heritage, a connection with nature and ancestors, as well as duties and respect.

The creation of these ornaments relies on natural materials, including seeds from diverse plant species, vines, feathers, teeth, and bones from wild animals. The passing down of this knowledge within families underscores the importance of intergenerational learning in safeguarding these rich cultural traditions.

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Figure 2. Headdresses crafted by the Bororo Indigenous people, made with feathers from the blue-and-yellow macaw (*Ara ararauna*), the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*), toucans (*Pteroglossus castanotis*), parrots, and hawks, belonging to the following subclans: (A) Bakoro ecerae; (B) Bokodori ecerae; (C) Kie; (D) Aroroe; (E) Apiborege; (F) Iwagudu. These Bororo artifacts, housed in the “Documentation Center and Permanent Exhibition of Adornments and Handicrafts” in Meruri village, were kindly made available for consultation and photographic documentation.

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 3. (A, B, C, D) Necklaces crafted by the Kaiowá Indigenous people, made with seeds from different plant species. Notably, necklace (A) is made with a peccary tooth; (E, F, G, H) Necklaces crafted by the Mura Indigenous people, made with seeds from the açai palm (*Euterpe oleracea*). Notably, necklace (E) is made with an alligator tooth (*Caiman* spp.).

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 4. Detail of the necklace-making process by the Tenharim Indigenous people, using seeds from the *tucumã* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*), native to the Amazon Rainforest: (A) Freshly harvested seed from the forest; (B) The seeds are broken with a machete into different sizes; (C) Pieces of seeds are manually drilled to allow the passage of thread; (D) A cotton thread is threaded through the holes in the seed pieces; (E) The seed pieces are sanded to achieve a smooth and uniform product of desired quality; (F) and (G) *Tucumã* palm seed necklace; (H) *Tucumã* palm seed necklace with howler monkey (*Sapajus apella*) and coati (*Nasua nasua*) teeth.

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 5. (A) Tenharim necklace made with *tamutu* seeds (*Canna indica*) and a peccary tooth (*Tayassu tajacu*); (B) Kaiowá necklace/bracelet made with "pau-brasil" seeds (*Adenanthera pavonina*); (C) Tenharim rings made with seeds from the *tucumã* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*); (D) and (F) Kaiowá necklaces made with seeds from different plant species; (G) Mura earrings made with seeds from the *açaí* palm (*Euterpe oleracea*), rubber tree seeds (*Hevea brasiliensis*), and feathers; (H) Tenharim earrings made with macaw feathers.

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 6. Some body adornments crafted by the Tenharim: (A) and (B) Bracelets (*tapakuras*) made with macaw feathers (*Ara* spp.); (C) Bracelets made with feathers from macaws, curassows (*Pauxi tuberosa*), and tinamou (*Crypturellus* spp.); (D) Armband made with straw from the *tucumã* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*) and bird feathers; (E) Headdress (*akanitara*) made with cotton and macaw feathers; (F) Detail of the traditional cotton (*mandijua*) weaving used to support macaw feathers in the headdress; (G) Hairpin made with macaw feathers; (H) Headdresses made with traditional cotton, macaw feathers, and curassow feathers.

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 7. (A) Bororo earrings made with golden grass (*Syngonanthus nitens*) and feathers. Tenharim necklaces crafted with: (B) Seeds from the *tucumã* palm (*Astrocaryum aculeatum*) and curassow bones (*Pauxi tuberosa*). At the ends, curassow feathers and seeds from the *inajá* (*Attalea maripa*) and *tucumã* palms, the lighter and darker ones, respectively; (C) Bark of the fruit from the castanha-de-arara tree (*Joannesia heveoides*); (D) *Tucumã* palm seeds combined with plastic; (E) Green *tucumã* seed; (F) Seeds from the *tucumãzinho* palm (*Astrocaryum gynacanthum*).

Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.